

1985 March 6

Eleventh NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000-7000: Step 2/3 (Lindegren, Söderhjelm)

Task 6220: Simulations Input data for Step 2/3 (abscissa values and associated star and RGC catalogues) have been generated for up to 20,000 stars and 2.5 years' observation. A tape with contents as described in NDAC/LO/048 (= C) was delivered to FAST in January. The task is thus completed.

Task 6230: Abscissa extraction A program to sort the abscissae according to star number has been written and tested. It takes as input data on the same format as generated in Task 6220 (and presumably similar to the Step 1 output) and produces a file or tape with sorted abscissae as required for the Step 2/3 proper (NDAC/LO/049 = C). This task is completed except for interfacing with the Step 1 output.

Tasks 6240-6270: Observation equations, formation and solution of normals

The main program ACCU23 for accumulating Step 2/3 normal equations now exists in all essential parts and is being tested with simulated data input from Tasks 6220-6230. The MESH algorithm and preadjustment of the astrometric parameters perform satisfactorily and we are working with the set zero points and global parameters, where there are still some bugs. A preliminary solution program (SOLV23) also exists and appears to work well.

WP8000: Double stars (Lindegren)

No new work to be reported.

Meetings

LL and SS attended two Scandinavian-NDAC meetings in this period. At the Second FAST Thinkshop (Marseilles 21-25 January), LL gave three papers on the NDAC reductions (NDAC/LO/050-052 = C179-181). At the 12th Meeting of the INCA Executive Committee (Bordeaux 19-20 February), a presentation was also given by LL on the reductions of Double Stars in particular, and on observability limitations (no written report available).

Working papers

- C Söderhjelm 1985-01-31: SIP23: Programs to simulate input data
(NDAC/LO/048) for Step 2/3 (final version)
- C Söderhjelm 1985-02-07 SOR23: A program to sort the input data
(NDAC/LO/049) for Step 2/3
- C179 Lindegren and van Leeuwen 1985-02-14: Attitude reconstitution by
(NDAC/LO/050) the NDAC (Proc. of the 2nd FAST Thinkshop)
- C180 Lindegren and Petersen 1985-02-22: Great circle reduction by the
(NDAC/LO/051) NDAC (Proc. of the 2nd FAST Thinkshop)
- C181 Lindegren and Söderhjelm 1985-02-25: Sphere reconstitution by the
(NDAC/LO/052) NDAC (Proc. of the 2nd FAST Thinkshop)
- C Lindegren 1985-02-15: Least-squares estimation of $B(t)$ by splines